

UNDERSTANDING THE DETAIL AND WEAR OF DETAILS AND KEYS OF VEHICLES

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***Annotation.** This article The perfection of the structure of vehicles and the high quality of preparation do not guarantee their long and uninterrupted operation. To do this, about the proper use of the machine and its proper maintenance*

***Keywords and phrases.**Operation without damage, repair, technical condition, wear, wear and tear, corrosion, wear, wear, wear resistance, friction, deformation, mechanical wear, molecular-mechanical wear, corrosion-mechanical wear, fretting-corrosion, cavitation wear , erosion erosion, erosion results, erosion intensity.*

Wear, rust, wear, tear and friction of vehicle parts

The perfection of the structure of vehicles and the high quality of preparation do not guarantee their long and uninterrupted operation. To do this, it is necessary to use the machine technically and repair it as intended. There is a great deal of experience in the use of cars in some industries. The relationship between the use of machines and their corrosion resistance is not sufficiently generalized. The methods of technical operation of vehicles are constantly changing, trying to find the most suitable method for the task of the car. With the development of technology and increasing their technical level, they can be used without repair.

During the operation of the vehicle, its technical condition gradually deteriorates: engine power decreases, technical speed decreases, fuel consumption increases, wear rate increases, driving comfort decreases, TCK and JT workload increases, reliability decreases. Vehicle wear can be divided into two types: the first type is physical wear, the second type is spiritual wear. Depreciation of cars is a

process of gradual and constant change in the operational properties of cars under the influence of mechanical, electrical, thermal and other loads. The presence of such loads is determined by the mode of operation and operating conditions of the vehicle. For example, rubber products lose their strength and elasticity (as a result of oxidation, exposure to heat or cold, chemical exposure to oils, fuels or liquids, exposure to moisture, exposure to solar radiation). Fats and oils are contaminated with edible products, their viscosity deteriorates, the strength of the additives is lost, etc. Obsolescence is the reduction in the cost of a vehicle that is operating under the influence of technical progress. The emergence of new, more productive cars and the decline in the performance of previously created cars will lead to the obsolescence of existing cars.

There are two forms of obsolescence in technology: the first is the reduction of the current price with a cheaper production of a new car of the same design, and the second is the depreciation of existing equipment as a result of the creation of more perfect (more productive) designs of machines. As a result of the development of technology with high images, existing machines become obsolete and can be replaced with new ones long before they become physically obsolete. Depreciation of machines is an economic category, which determines the degree of depreciation of existing equipment as a result of technical obsolescence of previous types of machines and lower production costs. The coefficient of reduction of the price due to technical development serves as a criterion of obsolescence of the car and is defined as follows:

Here: The criterion of moral obsolescence, expressed in shares of the starting price of cars; Starting price of Q-car, soums; The cost of production of the machine, taking into account the reduction of the starting price due to the creation of more advanced new designs of Qi.ch. machines, as well as the production of similar machines at low cost, soums.

Corrosion of vehicles. Corrosion is caused by the aggressive action of the environment on a detail. This oxidizes the metal, reduces its strength and deteriorates its appearance. The main causes of corrosion are salt solutions in the external

environment, acids in water and soil, and certain elements (elements) in exhaust gases. Body, cabin, frame, supply and cooling systems, pipelines are more prone to corrosion.

Destruction and wear of vehicles. Decomposition occurs when parts are subjected to periodic (cyclic) loads. Such loads exceed the tolerances of the parts. Gradual fatigue cracks lead to fatigue wear of parts after a certain number of loads. For example, springs, brackets, half-axles, frames, (mainly in difficult conditions).

Fragile and viscous decay. Fragile decay occurs without initial deformations, under the influence of normal stresses. The strength of the details depends to a large extent on the condition of the thin outer layer, as cracks usually appear in this layer. As the carbon content increases during refining, the strength of carbon steels increases. An increase in the amount of carbon leads to the formation of highly saturated carbon solutions in iron. The location of these solutions prevents movement and promotes the formation of cracks.

Exhaustion. Parts that fall under static and cyclic force loads (frame parts, crankshafts, spring boards, springs, connecting rods, etc.) wear out as a result of fatigue. Fatigue of metals is associated with elastic deformation. It leads to a complete loss of performance of parts. Heat decomposition occurs under the influence of heat. Some parts of the TV become hot during operation, as a result of which the structure previously formed in their objects is broken, and they lose their serviceability. Examples include cylinder heads, combustion chambers, pistons, exhaust manifolds, and pipes. Strength is the ability of a part to withstand a certain stress (flexibility limit) with respect to wear.

Erosion of TVs is the destruction of the outer layers of the interconnected part (detail) under the influence of frictional forces and the complex physicochemical processes that occur with them. Erosion is the result of wear and tear of interconnected parts, which manifests itself in changes in sizes, shapes, sizes and weights. As a result of corrosion, the working surfaces of the interconnect are destroyed, the kinematic connections are broken, and as a result, the node or mechanism fails.

Abrasion resistance is the ability of a part to resist corrosion under certain conditions of friction and is measured by a quantity that is inversely proportional to the rate or intensity of wear.

Friction (training) is the resistance that occurs when two interacting bodies move relative to each other. The work of friction is the elimination of frictional forces that occur in the path of displacement of objects (parts). The intensity of wear of parts depends on the work of friction, its path and friction conditions. For rotating parts, the friction path (for example, the bearing of a crankshaft) is found by multiplying the number of revolutions of the shaft by its circumference. For properly moving parts (such as piston rings), the number of strokes is multiplied by the number of strokes.

Deformation of details. Deformation mainly occurs when flexible (steel) or bent (cast iron) parts exceed the yield strength (steel) or strength limit (cast iron).